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VALIDATION STUDY OF 3D OSCILLATING COMPRESSOR CASCADE

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ABSTRACT

Given the importance of blade flutter, accurate and reliable predictions of the phenomenon have been continually pursued. With the growing use of highly three-dimensional blading designs, the capability to simulate three-dimensional aeroelastic mechanisms becomes more important than ever. It is noted that validation cases of unsteady CFD methods against experimental cases with detailed 3D unsteady pressures are still rather lacking.

In the present study, the modelling approach for unsteady aerodynamics induced by a three-dimensional oscillating compressor cascade is validated by the commercial solver CFX. The characteristics of non-linear phenomena such as laminar bubble separation and tip clearance flows are investigated with emphasis on their effects on the cascade overall aerodynamic damping. The results show that laminar bubble separation has negligible effects on the overall stability, while tip clearance has detrimental effects.

The validity of the influence coefficient method (ICM) is also examined. The comparison with a baseline ‘tuned’ cascade shows that the differences in predicting far-field behaviour are paramount, manifested by that a tuned cascade model may predict acoustic resonance but an ICM can’t. On the other hand, non-linearity effects closely relevant to the basic linear assumption of the ICM are shown to be only a small influence. The present results thus suggest that when validating a tuned cascade CFD model against data from an ICM based experimental model, care should be taken in choosing compatible far-field boundary conditions. Otherwise, different results may arise substantially or entirely from the inherently different far-field predictability between the two models rather than those typical numerical and physical modelling aspects of interest (e.g. meshing, spatial and temporal discretization errors, turbulence modelling, geometrical modelling and impacts).

NOMENCLATURE

IBPA	interblade phase angle
ICM	Influence Coefficient Method
PS	pressure surface
PV	passage vortex
SS	suction surface
TLV	tip leakage vortex
TWM	Travelling Wave Mode
Am_l	local bending amplitude
Am_{tip}	tip bending amplitude
Ap_1	amplitude of the first harmonic pressure
C	blade chord
C_{ax}	blade axial chord
$ Cp_1 $	amplitude of the 1 st harmonic pressure coefficient
Cp	blade surface pressure coefficient
f	frequency
h	blade span/height
k	reduced frequency
P_{01}	mid-span inlet total pressure
P_{02}	outlet total pressure
P_2	outlet static pressure
V_{ref}	reference isentropic exit velocity
x	axial chordwise distance
z	spanwise location
β_1	inlet flow angle, relative to axial direction
ξ	overall aerodynamic damping coefficient
ξ_c	spanwise aerodynamic damping coefficient
ξ_l	local aerodynamic damping coefficient
σ	interblade phase angle IBPA

1. BACKGROUND AND INTRODUCTION

Among the blade aeroelasticity problems, flutter is a common phenomenon that affects blade rows with a high aspect ratio such as frontal stages of compressors and rear stages of turbines. Previous researchers have shown that the

mechanisms of flutter are complex and many factors are involved. Two basic variables are widely known to have a dominating effect, namely reduced frequency and inter-blade phase angle [1].

Böls and Fransson [2] presented the test results of several compressor and turbine cascades at various flow regimes and oscillation modes. However, the published detailed measurements are usually limited at mid-span sections. Given the 3D nature of turbomachine blades, the understanding of three-dimensional features on the aeroelastic stability is important. Widely developed CFD solvers for blade flutter prediction also need 3D experimental cases for validation. Previously, Yang and He [3] carried out an experiment to measure the spanwise damping distribution on the compressor cascade at different tip clearances. A similar experiment was done by Huang et al. [4] but on a linear turbine cascade. Further research on the same cascade was carried out experimentally and computationally with the part-span shrouds [5]. More recently, a similar effort was initiated to establish a detailed 3D study of the oscillating steam turbine blades [6].

Tip leakage flow is a typical three-dimensional flow feature that has attracted much attention from various researchers in the past. It is widely accepted that tip clearance is detrimental to compressor's aerodynamic efficiency and stall inception [7] [8]. Fewer researchers study the effects of tip clearance on the compressor flutter stability. Yang and He [3] showed experimentally that the tip clearance has destabilizing effects for all interblade phase angles and most of the blade span. Besem and Kielb [9] investigated the effects of tip clearance at torsion mode by a harmonic balance code. They found that the minimum damping initially increases with the gap size until it reaches maximum. Overall, the tip gap has stabilizing effects compared to no tip case. Fu et al. [10] showed that the minimum damping decreases with increasing tip gap until it reaches a minimum threshold. This finding is in contrast with the study of Besem and Kielb [9]. Hence, the observations from previous studies of tip-leakage flow effects on the compressor blade aeroelastic stability are still inconclusive.

The present work is prompted by the lack of detailed 3D experimental data for oscillating blades and the validation of 3D unsteady CFD solvers. The objectives are mainly twofold:

- 1) To validate a commercial solver (CFX) for the unsteady aerodynamics induced by a three-dimensional oscillating compressor cascade.
- 2) Examine the validity of the aerodynamic influence coefficient method and its implication.

2. TEST CASE

Test Case Description

The compressor blade profile used in this study is the controlled-diffusion blading proposed by Elazar et al. [11], which has been studied extensively for its steady performance in modern blade profile designs. The blading was utilised in an oscillating cascade test but operated at a reduced Reynolds number. At the original design Reynolds

Figure 1: Experimental linear cascade configuration for influence coefficient method with only the middle (reference ‘0’) blade oscillating (reproduced from [3])

number $Re = 7 \times 10^5$, there is no bubble separation identifiable. The same blading was adopted in an oscillating cascade experiment at a lower Reynolds number of $Re = 1.95 \times 10^5$ (Yang and He [3]). At this lower Re , a laminar bubble separation forms on the suction surface. Recently, He and Yi [12] employed a high fidelity two-scale methodology for URANS/LES to study this blade profile, also predicting the separation bubble.

Although the cascade was studied at a low-speed condition, it involves with various important features in gas turbine aerodynamic blading design including laminar bubble separation and tip clearance. The detailed measurement on the blade surfaces, especially in the near tip region makes this case suitable for validating modelling techniques and methods, and for exploring and understanding flow physics.

Data Reduction

A tuned cascade is characterised by all blades oscillating at the same frequency, the same amplitude and a constant phase angle difference between adjacent blades (IBPA). Effectively all the blades in the bladerow are oscillating in a circumferential traveling wave pattern, thus a tuned cascade model is also known as a travelling wave mode (TWM). The unsteady pressures along a blade surface are collected during a period of vibration. The unsteady pressures are decomposed into temporal Fourier harmonic components:

$$p(t) = a_0 + \sum_n [a_n \cos(n\omega t) + b_n \sin(n\omega t)] = a_0 + \sum_n A_p \sin(n\omega t + \phi_1) \quad (1)$$

For a blade oscillation in 1st harmonic motion, the local damping can be calculated from the amplitude and phase angle of the first harmonic pressure:

$$\xi_l = \frac{-\pi A m_l |C_{p1}| \sin(\phi_1)}{A m_{tip}} \quad (2)$$

The overall damping is calculated by integrating the local damping along the blade chord and span:

$$\xi_c = \int_0^C \frac{-\pi A m_l |C_{p1}| \sin(\phi_1)}{C A m_{tip}} ds \quad (3)$$

$$\xi = \frac{1}{h} \int_0^h \xi_c dz \quad (4)$$

Figure 2: Damping contributions of influence coefficients from the oscillating blade and its neighbouring blades (IBPA = 0° and k=0.4)

The influence coefficient method (ICM) is employed in both the experimental and the present computational study to obtain the overall damping at different interblade phase angle (IBPA). The assumption of the ICM is a tuned cascade and linear behaviour of the unsteady pressure thus the validity of superposition.

The key feature, particularly important for experimental setups, is only one blade (blade ‘0’ in the middle, Fig.1) in the cascade needs to be oscillated. Under the assumption of linear superposition, the unsteady aerodynamic influences on a reference blade from all oscillating blades in a cascade is equivalent to the sum of unsteady aerodynamic influences of one blade oscillating on itself and on all other non-oscillating blades in the cascade. Therefore, the first harmonic pressure coefficient of the reference blade (central blade) can be calculated as a sum of first harmonic pressure coefficients from oscillating itself and its neighbouring stationary blades:

$$C_{p1} = \sum_{m=-3}^{+3} C_{p1}(m) e^{-im\sigma} \quad (5)$$

The IBPA σ is defined as positive for a forward travelling wave mode, where blade +1 leads blade 0 (see Fig.1).

3. NUMERICAL METHOD

Computational Domain Configuration

The computational study is conducted in the time domain. The central blade is oscillated in the bending mode, whereas other blades are kept stationary as in the influence coefficient method. The experimental rig has a seven-blade configuration and tunnel walls. However, a five-blade configuration and a direct periodic boundaries are used for this study to reduce mesh count. This is justified because the contribution of two outermost blades (Blade +3 and Blade -3) are insignificant as shown in Fig. 2.

Boundary Conditions

The commercial solver CFX 18.2 is used for the simulation. The inlet boundary conditions include total pressure, total temperature, and flow direction. The static atmospheric pressure is used at the outlet. The blades, hub, and casing surfaces are modelled as an adiabatic no-slip wall. For unsteady simulations, the central reference blade is displaced periodically with a prescribed motion derived

Figure 3: Multi-passage mesh and close up on the boundary layer near the leading edge

linearly from the tip and hub bending amplitudes. Translational periodicity is applied at two outermost interfaces to represent an infinite linear cascade. For unsteady simulation of tip clearance cases, the volume mesh of tip region above the central blade is periodically deformed together with the central blade mesh to avoid mesh folding.

Mesh Independence Study

Meshing is carried out in ICEM to generate a high-quality structured hexahedral volume mesh. HOH topology is used to create H mesh in the inlet and outlet blocks. The main domain containing the blades are modelled with O grid around the blade surfaces to resolve the boundary layers. Fig. 3 shows a computational multi-passage mesh with local refined mesh in leading edge, trailing edge boundary layer and wake regions.

The tip clearance is modelled as gridded tip, which provides a smooth transition of fluid flow from the passage to the tip region. To ensure that the mesh resolution is sufficient, simulations of three mesh level are carried out for a three-dimensional single passage. The blade surface pressures are monitored and compared. The final mesh resolution is sufficiently fine to capture the flow physics.

Figure 4: Gridded tip mesh for 1% tip clearance

Figure 5: Sensitivity to turbulence transition model

The final mesh size has 280x75x100 elements in an axial, circumferential, and radial direction. An extra 19 radial elements are required for each 1% span of tip clearance as shown in Fig. 4. This mesh resolution yields approximately two million mesh cells for one 3D blade passage.

Sensitivity to Turbulence Modelling

The laminar bubble separation is captured on the suction surface in the experiment. In the computational study, the turbulence sensitivity shows that only the two-equation γ - θ transition correlation coupled with the SST model [13] is able to predict the separation bubble numerically. Fig. 5 shows the ability of the transitional model to predict the separation bubble on the suction surface from approximately 30% to 50% chord. This computed bubble separation agrees with the experimental results, whereas the boundary layer remains attached if the fully turbulent model is used.

4. STEADY FLOW RESULTS

Effects of Inlet Endwall Boundary Layer Thickness

One of the steady flow feature of this cascade as experimentally observed is the unloading effect near the endwall. If the uniform total pressure is applied at the inlet, insignificant unloading near the endwall can be observed in the computational results. Fig. 6 presents the steady pressure distributions at 50% and 95% span for the simulation with the uniform inlet boundary condition. There is hardly any unloading in the tip region in the computed results, clearly in discrepancy with the experimental data.

Figure 6: Steady pressure distributions at 50% and 95% spans respectively (clean inlet)

Figure 7: Steady pressure distributions at 50% and 95% span sections with inlet boundary layer thickness [3].

The passage-averaged inlet total pressure distribution is extracted from the experiment and applied to the simulation. Using the inlet endwall boundary layer as reported in Yang and He [3], a significant unloading effects can be observed at 95% span as shown in Fig. 7. In fact, with this inlet boundary layer profile, the computation seems to over-predict the unloading effects.

To gauge the sensitivity to the inlet boundary layer, the original inlet boundary layer thickness is varied proportionally to match the experimental steady pressure distribution results. The total pressure loss coefficient is defined as:

$$Yp = \frac{P_{01} - P_0}{P_{01} - P_2} \quad (6)$$

Fig. 8 presents different inlet boundary layer profiles, which are considered and tested numerically. The total pressure profile with an inlet boundary layer thickness about 5% span thinner compared to that measured originally in the experiment is chosen due to its best match with the experiment. This is approximately the same size as what was measured and reported by Williams et al. [14] for the same cascade under the same flow conditioning. Fig. 9 shows the well-matched steady pressure distributions at 50% and 95% span with the adjusted boundary layer profile.

Clearly, the mid span separation bubble is well captured, so is the unloading of tip region.

Figure 8: Total pressure inlet profile with different endwall boundary layer thickness

Figure 9: Steady pressure distribution of the central blade without tip clearance at 50% and 95% span, with inlet boundary layer thickness comparable to that of [14]

Figure 10: Steady surface pressure distributions at 95% span with two tip clearance gaps

Effects of Tip Clearance

A key feature of this cascade test case is the presence of tip clearance. Fig. 10 presents the steady pressure distributions at 95% span for different tip clearance gaps. The tip clearance has been observed to have a local effect near the endwall. Hence, the steady pressure distributions at the majority of blade span remain largely unaffected and are not shown here.

a) No tip clearance

b) Tip clearance 1%

Figure 11: Total pressure contours at $0.2C$ downstream of trailing edge

Figure 12: Overall aerodynamic damping at $k=0.4$

The chordwise local effects of tip clearance are also captured. From the leading edge to about 30% chord, pressures on the suction surface increase as the tip gap increases. On the other hand, from about 30% chord to the trailing edge, pressures on the suction surface decrease, as the tip gap increases. The pressures on the pressure surfaces remain unchanged. Thus as the tip gap increases, there is an opposite trend in loading variations: an unloading in the frontal part and an uploading in the rear part. The computed

local loading variations with the tip gap agree well with those of the experiment.

Fig. 11 shows the total pressure loss coefficient contours at the traverse plane $0.2C_x$ downstream of the trailing edge. A tip leakage vortex can be seen to increase the total pressure loss compared to the zero tip clearance configuration. The mid-span and hub regions remain unaffected by the tip leakage vortex. It confirms that tip clearance is the local effect near the casing endwall.

Secondary velocity vectors are also plotted in Fig. 11 to illustrate vortical flow structures. For the no-tip clearance configuration, the passage vortices (PV) driven by the cross-passage pressure gradient are symmetrical between the casing shroud and hub (Fig. 11a). The PV near casing rotates clockwise, whereas the passage vortex near hub rotates anti-clockwise. With tip clearance (Fig. 11b), the vortex of anti-clockwise circulation takes place near the shroud due to tip leakage vortex (TLV), driven by the pressure difference between the pressure surface and suction surface of the same blade. There is a clear interference between the tip leakage vortex and the passage vortex. And the passage vortex appears to be much smaller and weaker than that in the case with zero tip clearance. In addition, the passage vortex is pushed away from the suction surface side and further into the mid-passage region. These findings are in line with previous researches in aerodynamic performance of tip leakage flow [7] [15].

5. UNSTEADY FLOW RESULTS

Aeroelastic Damping for Tuned Cascade

Fig. 12 shows the overall damping at reduced frequency $k = 0.4$. The CFD results are in good agreement with the experiment. The least stable IBPA lies in the forward travelling wave mode, at about 20 to 30 degrees.

Detailed Unsteady Pressures at Least Stable IBPA

Fig. 13 presents the first harmonic unsteady pressure amplitude and phase responses at the least stable IBPA. The first harmonic amplitudes decreases along the chord for both suction and pressure surfaces. The computational unsteady pressure amplitudes at 50% span are well-matched with the experimental results. At 95% span, some discrepancies can be observed in the frontal chord of the pressure surface. The distribution of phase angles shows that CFD results seem to be more unstable in the suction surface and more stable in the pressure surface. These effects seem to counter-balance and hence the predicted overall damping is only slightly more stable than that of the experiment.

Aeroelastic Effects of Separation Bubble

The mid-span laminar bubble separation has been shown to affect the steady pressure distribution on the suction surface. In this section, its effects on the aeroelastic stability are examined by comparing the 2D mid-span sections. To highlight the aeroelastic stability variation not only with the chordwise location, but also with IBPA, we choose the local aero-damping contours on an x - σ map, as shown in Fig. 14. It shows the mid-span distributions of local aerodynamic damping along the chord as its abscissa with the entire range of IBPAs as its ordinate.

Figure 13: Amplitudes and phases of the unsteady pressures at least stable IBPA

a) **Experimental** (SS at mid span, $k = 0.4$)

b) **2D transitional** (SS at mid span, $k = 0.4$)

c) **2D fully turbulent** (SS at mid span, $k = 0.4$)

Figure 14: Local damping contours (on IBPA- x/C plane) for suction surface at mid-span (transitional and fully turbulent models vs experimental results)

From Fig. 14c, we can see that the fully turbulent model produces a continuously smooth local damping distribution on the suction surface for an entire range of IBPAs. At the least stable IBPA ($\sigma=0^\circ-90^\circ$), the whole suction surface is marginally stable from the leading edge to the trailing edge. The transitional model shows strong variations in local damping distribution, particularly at extreme IBPAs. The locations of local damping fluctuations as shown in Fig. 14b reflect the locations of the bubble separation formation and

Figure 15: Overall aerodynamic damping at $k=0.4$ for transitional and fully turbulent models

the reattachment at around 30% and 60% chord. The transitional model can predict qualitatively the effects of the laminar separation bubble compared to the experimental results shown in Fig. 14a, whereas the fully turbulent model completely misses this behaviour. The pressure surface is insensitive to the bubble separation formation, hence its local damping distribution remains unaffected regardless of the turbulence model choice. This finding suggests that the local damping is dependent on the state of the surface boundary layer. If the flow is fully turbulent as on the pressure surface, the choice between the transitional $\gamma-\theta$ model and the conventional SST fully turbulent model does not yield significant difference.

Fig. 15 shows the overall damping at the mid-span section calculated by taking integrations along the blade chord. Despite the remarkable differences in the suction surface local damping between the transitional and fully turbulent models, the overall damping values over the entire chord are very similar. Therefore, for the present case, the suction surface laminar bubble separation does not seem to have a significant effect on the overall aeroelastic stability.

Figure 16: Overall aerodynamic damping at $k=0.4$ for different tip clearance settings

Aeroelastic Effects of Tip Clearance

Fig. 16 shows the effects of tip clearance on the overall damping. It can be seen that the least stable damping decreases as the tip gap increases. The least stable IBPA

remains almost the same, to be about 20~30 degrees. The predicted destabilizing trend of increasing tip clearance is captured qualitatively across the entire range of IBPA, compared to the experiment. When the tip gap increases from zero to 2% span, the minimum damping is numerically predicted to decrease by 28%. From the experiment, the minimum damping is reduced by around 27% compared to that at the nominal zero tip-gap condition. This is effectively comparable to reducing the reduced frequency by a half [3].

6. ON VALIDITY OF INFLUENCE COEFFICIENT METHOD (ICM)

Many recent experiments for oscillating blades use the influence coefficient method to obtain data of unsteady pressure and aerodynamic damping for a tuned cascade due to its simplicity and convenience in experimental setup, instrumentation and data acquisition. In a more realistic tuned cascade, all blades vibrate in a travelling wave mode at a constant IBPA. In addition to the basic assumption of linear superposition which obviously needs to be examined, what are other factors?

Note that the influence coefficient method is effectively a sum of sine and cosine functions for any given IBPA (Eq.5). Hence, the damping variation with IBPA will always be smooth and sinusoidal. However, LINSUB [16], a 2D semi-analytical code for unsteady flows past a tuned flat plate cascade, shows clearly unsmooth aerodynamic damping curve, as seen in Fig. 17. These spikes are due to the dynamic behaviour of the inlet and outlet ducts rather than the bladerow itself. The spikes in the unsteady responses happen around a resonance condition of a duct acoustic mode corresponding to certain circumferential wave length and traveling speed (thus frequency and IBPA).

It should be recognised that a tuned cascade will excite an acoustic mode when the frequency and IBPA match the circumferential wave length (number of nodal diameters) and traveling speed of the acoustic mode. On the other hand, the ICM configuration with only one blade oscillating won't be able to excite such a duct acoustic mode.

Noting the inability for single oscillating blade to excite an acoustic mode (thus for the ICM to predict acoustic resonance), we would like to further examine what this might mean and imply when using ICM generated data and results, in particular, in terms of far-field inlet and outlet conditions.

Test Configurations and Conditions

In order to examine the sensitivity of the aeroelastic response of the cascade to the far-field treatment, the inlet and outlet duct length are varied to alter the acoustic behaviour of the system. Test cases are a combination of the following parameters:

- 1) Domain size (duct length): short (1C upstream, 2C upstream), long inlet (6C upstream, 2C upstream), long outlet (1C upstream, 6C downstream), long inlet and outlet (6C upstream, 6C downstream);
- 2) Flow regime: low speed (subsonic), high speed (transonic, maximum Mach number ~1.0-1.1);
- 3) Bending amplitude: 6%C and 3%C for the low speed flow; 1%C and 0.5%C for the high speed flows.

Figure 17: Typical aerodynamic damping variation with IBPA, predicted by LINSUB (bending mode, $k=0.6$)

Figure 18: Nonlinearity effects at low speed

The Fourier Transformation method implemented in CFX in a double passage domain with the phase-shifted periodicity is used for TWM simulations. In this method, the flow history on the phase-shifted periodic boundaries are stored and reconstructed using Fourier series, which is based on the work of He [17].

Low-speed Cases

Under the assumptions of the influence coefficient method, two aspects must be fulfilled. The first aspect is a sufficient decay of unsteady pressure responses in the neighbouring blades away from the reference blade. This requirement has been shown at the beginning of this study in Fig.2, where other blades in the cascade have small contribution to the overall damping compared to the central blade. Only two adjacent blades (Blade +1 and Blade -1) and the central blade (Blade 0) contribute significantly to the overall damping, which makes the five-blade configuration justified for this computational study.

The second aspect is the linearity assumption, particularly for this cascade due to the presence of laminar bubble separation, which is seemingly nonlinear indicated by the local non-smooth damping variation (Fig.14a and Fig. 14b). However, as shown in Fig. 15, the bubble separation has negligible effect on the overall damping at a given spanwise section.

Figure 19: Effects of duct length at low σ speed and $k=0.6$

Figure 20: Mach number contours of high-speed case

A further test of the linearity is carried out by comparing the overall damping curves computed at two bending amplitudes, as shown in Fig.18. The damping curves calculated using ICM from the two amplitudes remain constant, hence the non-linearity is negligible at the low-speed regime. This finding agrees with previous studies, where the non-linear effects of the laminar bubble separation are observed to be negligible [3]. Also shown in Fig. 18, the inlet/outlet duct lengths show negligible effects on the calculated overall damping calculated, indicating that the ICM model is quite insensitive to far-field conditions.

Fig. 19 presents the overall damping of configurations with different duct lengths by both the influence coefficient method and the tuned cascade model. The minimum damping predicted by the turned cascade method for the configuration with long duct at outlet reduces by 78% compared to that of the short configuration. In addition, the spiky variation of the damping at some IBPAs can be seen in the forward-travelling wave mode (with a positive IBPA) for the configuration with long ducts at both the inlet and outlet. Also of interest, the spiky damping behaviour is observed at both vibration amplitudes (3%C and 6%C). The similarity in the results between the two amplitudes again underlines the linearity of unsteady flow responses in this condition.

High-speed Cases

The experimental rig is in low-speed regime. Although we have had some useful observations, it would be naturally of interest to ask what we should expect in its high speed counterpart with seemingly more nonlinear transonic flows.

Figure 21: Unsteady pressure responses on the suction surface of the central blade B0 in the ICM method

To address this, the current cascade is further studied numerically in a high-speed regime by reducing the static pressure at outlet ($P_2/P_{01} \approx 0.82$). The maximum isentropic Mach number of the blade is about 1.0~1.1 on the suction surface as shown in Fig. 20.

At this flow condition, the blade is oscillated in the bending mode at different amplitudes. The unsteady pressure responses show a bump in the first harmonic unsteady pressure amplitude on the suction surface, at the location where the isentropic Mach number enters the transonic regime. Comparisons of the unsteady pressure coefficients of the central oscillating blade by the ICM method (Fig. 21) show that this transonic bump is sensitive to the bending amplitude, an indication of nonlinearity. At the small bending amplitude, the flow is largely linear. As the bending amplitude increases, the non-linearity increases as can be seen from the unsteady pressure responses at tip bending amplitudes 3% and 6%.

On the numerical convergence, the travelling wave mode simulations at a high speed tend to be more difficult to achieve convergence to a periodic state. Additional numerical damping have to be applied for the high speed cases to remove numerical noises from a solution. It is noted that when a strong numerical damping is applied, the acoustic response in the far field can also be damped significantly, and the overall damping will become smooth and sinusoidal as in the influence coefficient method.

Fig. 22 presents the overall damping variation with IBPA for different configurations by both the ICM and TWM method. In contrast to the case of the low speed flow,

the extended duct tends to stabilise the minimum damping. Looking at the damping variation more closely around the least stable IBPA (Fig.23), we can see that the minimum damping predicted by the travelling wave model for the configuration with long ducts at both inlet and outlet increases by 67% compared to that of the short configuration. Clear sensitivities of the damping values to the inlet outlet duct length, can be observed for the results predicted by the TWM method. On the other hand, the overall damping curves predicted by the ICM method remains sinusoidal and largely unaffected by the extended inlet/outlet ducts.

The main summary observation for the high speed case is that the primary factor on the validity and applicability of influence coefficient method is still the difference in predicting far field behaviour. The nonlinear effects, while being clearly higher in the transonic flow than in its low-speed counterpart, remain to be secondary.

Further Discussion

The present computational studies indicate that the linear assumption of the influence coefficient method is largely adequate for a range of flow conditions of practical interest, even in a transonic flow. So the influence coefficient model per se seems to be largely valid, at least as shown for the present cases tested.

However, we do see considerable differences in the results between the influence coefficient model and the tuned cascade model. And the differences are clearly dependent on IBPA for a given frequency. The prevailing factor causing the differences is attributed to the inherent different ability in capturing far-field behaviour, manifested by that a tuned oscillating cascade model can excite an acoustic resonance in an annulus duct whilst an influence coefficient model cannot. Consequently a tuned cascade model is clearly sensitive to the inlet and outlet far-field treatments. An influence coefficient method on the other hand, is largely insensitive to the far-field modelling, as shown in the present results.

It is therefore meaningful to make a distinction between the validity of the ICM model itself, and the applicability of the ICM for practical purposes. The present observations suggest that care should be taken in when comparing the results between ICM and TWM for validation purposes:

i) *If it is the far field behaviour that is of interest, then ICM model should not be used.*

ii) *If the interest is in validating the near-field physical and numerical modelling aspects for oscillating blade rows (e.g. mesh, turbulence modelling, time and spatial discretization, geometrical modelling, unsteady viscous flow physics and impacts), an ICM model can be useful. However a comparison with a tuned cascade model should be made only when a compatible far-field conditions are adopted (e.g., a perfect non-reflective far-field condition for a turned cascade may not be a good choice at all, when comparing with experimental data from ICM).*

Figure 22: Overall damping variation with IBPA at high speed ($k=0.2$)

Figure 23: Overall damping around least stable IBPA (close up of Fig.22 for IBPA=0 - 45deg).

CONCLUSIONS

The present study consists of two parts. In the first part, the unsteady CFD solver for oscillating blades as implemented in CFX has been validated against the detailed 3D experimental data of an oscillating compressor cascade. This is one of only few validation studies against detailed 3D unsteady aerodynamic experimental data available in the public domain. The following observations have been made:

- 1) The two-equation γ - θ transitional turbulence model can successfully capture the laminar bubble separation, as seen in the experiment.
- 2) A significant offloading locally in the tip region is seen to be caused by the inlet endwall boundary layer. The local offloading and its dependence on the tip gap variation can be predicted only if an adequate inlet endwall boundary layer is specified.
- 3) The laminar bubble separation affects local aerodynamic damping distribution on the suction surface. However, it yields insignificant effects on the overall damping.
- 4) Tip clearance is shown to have consistently a destabilizing effect on the aeroelastic stability of the compressor cascade.

In the second part, the validity and applicability of the influence coefficient method (ICM) are examined, leading to the following observations:

- 1) The unsteady flow response in this cascade is predominantly linear for both low speed and high speed conditions. Although some non-linear behaviour can be identified in the local transonic flow region, the linear assumption adopted in the ICM seems to hold reasonably well. The present results thus support the validity of the ICM model per se.
- 2) The main difference between the ICM and the tuned cascade model arises from the inherently different predictabilities between the two models in relation to the far-field acoustic behaviour. A tuned oscillating cascade model can excite an acoustic resonance whilst the single oscillating blade in the ICM model cannot. This also leads to distinctively different sensitivities of the two models to far-field conditions and treatments.
- 3) Applicability of the ICM will thus need to be considered accordingly when using it for validations. If the far-field behaviour is of interest, ICM should not be used. If on the other hand, the interest is in the near-field physical and numerical modelling aspects for an oscillating blade row, an ICM model can be useful. However a comparison with a tuned cascade model should be made only when compatible far-field treatments are adopted.

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